

EFFECT OF SURFACE FUNCTIONALIZATION OF GRAPHENE PARTICLES ON THE PROPERTIES OF NANOCOMPOSITES

Annika C. Ackermann¹, Stefan Carosella¹, Peter Middendorf¹ and Bronwyn L. Fox²

¹ University of Stuttgart, Institute of Aircraft Design, Stuttgart, Germany

² Swinburne University of Technology, Manufacturing Futures Research Institute, Melbourne, Australia

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluates the effect of a plasma treatment of graphene particles to produce a graphene material with an amine-functionalized surface to aid the dispersion process and the integration of these nano-inclusions into a polymeric matrix. The powder samples were characterized with regard to their chemical composition, morphology, level of defects, and specific surface area. The functionalized graphene material demonstrated a rougher surface and the chemical composition of its surface showed higher oxygen and lower carbon levels than the plane of the unfunctionalized material, but was similar to the edges of the unfunctionalized graphene. The change in the level of disorder and the specific surface area between the functionalized and unfunctionalized material was marginal. The presence of functional groups on the graphene particles aided the dispersion process by reducing the occurring peak line pressure in a three roll mill. Nonetheless, increasing loadings of both functionalized and unfunctionalized graphene, and smaller gap widths increased the present line pressures. When comparing the reaction enthalpy during curing of the pristine epoxy with the nanocomposite samples with a loading of 0.5 wt% of graphene, an increase of 9 % was observed in the case of unfunctionalized graphene and 13 % in the case of functionalized graphene.

1 INTRODUCTION

Increasing demands on the thermal, mechanical and electrical properties of composite materials require the incorporation of new materials such as graphene. Due to the particular arrangement of its carbon atoms, graphene demonstrates outstanding mechanical, thermal and electrical properties [1-3] whilst having a very large surface area [4]. This allows a significant change of the material properties of composite materials at very low filler loadings.

However, the integration of graphene into polymers poses a number of challenges as the graphene particles tend to form aggregates which can later act as failure points in the composite [5, 6]. A number of researchers try to overcome this issue by the use of different solvents [7-10], but these come at the cost of environmental issues, additional time-intensive processing steps and residual impurities which can influence the cross-linking process and, hence, alter the properties of the matrix significantly [11, 12]. In contrast to this, a tailored functionalization of the surface of the graphene particles can facilitate a homogeneous dispersion of the graphene particles in the polymer whilst improving the interfacial bonds between the particle and the polymer [13, 14].

This work examines the effect of an amine functionalization on the chemical composition, morphology, specific surface area and quality of graphene particles as well as the dispersion process and reaction enthalpy of graphene-including nanocomposites with an epoxy matrix.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Materials

Sika Deutschland GmbH (Germany) supplied the epoxy resin Biresin® CR83 and the amine-based hardener Biresin® CH83-10. It is a two-part resin system with a low mixed viscosity (155 mPa.s at 25 °C) which further aids the dispersion of the graphene particles.

Two varieties of graphene in the form of reduced graphene oxide were provided by Graphit Kropfmühl GmbH (Germany). Both of them were produced by a modified Hummer's method using the same batch of 500 μm graphite flakes as the starting material. EXG 98 300 R was used as the unfunctionalized material whereas EXG 98 300 R FNH underwent a cold plasma process with NH_3 being the source for the low-pressure gas plasma and, thus, creating an amine functionalization on the graphene particles. The unfunctionalized graphene (rGO) as well as the functionalized graphene (frGO) were used as received.

2.2 Preparation of nanocomposite samples

The three roll mill 80E from EXAKT Advanced Technologies GmbH was used to disperse the graphene particles within the epoxy resin. It was operated at a speed ratio of 1:3:9 where the velocity of the fastest roller was equal to 200 rpm. The material was led through the mill using eight cycles where the respective gap widths followed the procedure as shown in Table 1. After this dispersion process, the hardener was added and the suspension was subsequently stirred by hand and degassed for 10 min in a vacuum chamber.

Cycle number	Width of first gap (μm)	Width of second gap (μm)
1	90	30
2	90	30
3	60	20
4	60	20
5	30	10
6	30	10
7	15	5
8	15	5

Table 1: Gap widths used for the dispersion process of the different suspensions in the three roll mill.

2.3 Characterization methods

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) were performed on the powder samples placed on carbon tape with a Zeiss Auriga Crossbeam electron and ion beam microscope and an EDAX detector. At least three different areas of each sample were investigated.

Raman spectroscopy was carried out using a NT-MDT NTEGRA Spectra system with a 488 nm laser at a power of 4.5 mW and a 50x objective lens. The measurement procedure was carried out in accordance to the Good Practice Guide No. 145 by the National Physical Laboratory [15]. The powder was deposited on double-sided tape being placed on a glass slide. Five different spots of each material were evaluated with two accumulations of 10 s each.

Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) theory was executed on the rGO and frGO material using a Micromeritics TriStar 3000 and based on DIN ISO 9277:2010. The mass of each sample was in the range of 0.2-0.3 g and the samples were prepared for analysis for 20 min under the influence of a vacuum at 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and subsequently left to cool to room temperature. Nitrogen was used as the gaseous adsorbate and the respective BET specific surface area was calculated for each material based on five measurement points.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was conducted on the pristine epoxy and the nanocomposite samples using a DSC 2920 from TA Instruments. The samples were heated from room temperature to 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a heating rate of 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$.

The significance of the respective factors on the experimental data was assessed for a 95 % confidence interval.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Characterization of graphene particles

SEM images were used to establish the morphology of the powder samples. Figure 1 illustrates the respective morphology of graphite, rGO and frGO at a lower and higher magnification level. As expected, the graphite material exhibits a large lateral size and thickness with many layers of graphene stacked on top of each other. When comparing the images taken at 3.00 kV of rGO and frGO (cf. Figure 1(c) and Figure 1(e)), the frGO appears brighter. As edges are sources for increased electron emission in SEM measurements, the brighter surface of the frGO particles could be attributed to a rougher surface which was caused by the plasma treatment.

Figure 1: SEM images of (a, b) graphite, (c, d) rGO and (e, f) frGO.

The elemental composition of the powder samples was analyzed using EDX and is illustrated in Figure 2. It can be concluded that five key elements were present on the surface of the samples: carbon, oxygen, sodium, silicon, and sulfur. The levels of nitrogen caused by the plasma processing of the frGO particles are likely to be too low to be detected by EDX. As expected, carbon is the principal element in all materials. Given that a modified Hummer's method is used for the production of the examined graphene materials, oxygen atoms are introduced during this manufacturing process and cannot be completely removed from the structure of the graphene particles. When comparing the carbon and oxygen contents on the edges of rGO and frGO, no significant differences in the elemental composition can be detected. All other materials, and consequently also the plane and the edges of rGO, show significant differences in the carbon and oxygen levels. The edges of the rGO material consist of 17 % less carbon atoms and approximately five times higher oxygen levels than the plane of the rGO particles. No variation between the plane and the edges of the frGO particles can be noticed, but it consists of 12 % less carbon atoms and approximately five times more oxygen atoms than the plane of the rGO material. This variation in the elemental composition of the surface of the different graphene materials influences the chemical bonding of these samples with the polymeric matrix, but the particles will have a similar composition and, hence, similar properties below their surface. The presence of sodium and sulfur can be attributed to residues from the production process of rGO whereas silicon is a common impurity in naturally occurring graphite [16].

Figure 2: Elemental composition with respective standard error of graphite and graphene materials as determined using EDX spectra.

The Raman spectra of the powder materials are illustrated in Figure 3 where the results of the different measurement spots are consecutively shifted by 50 a.u. on the y-axis to aid the reader. Given that none of the particles is a single or bilayer graphene, only a small 2D-peak ($\sim 2700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) can be detected for all samples. Table 2 lists the ratio of D- to G-peak and the ratio of the 2D- to G-peak of the carbon materials. The peak intensity ratio I_D/I_G of the D-peak ($\sim 1350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and the G-peak ($\sim 1580 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) can be used to approximate the level of disorder within graphene samples. The difference in the level of disorder between rGO and frGO is not significant.

Figure 3: Raman spectra of five measurement spots with the respective intensity being shifted consecutively by 50 a.u. of (a) graphite, (b) rGO and (c) frGO.

	Graphite	rGO	frGO
I_D/I_G	0.60 ± 0.04	0.62 ± 0.04	0.59 ± 0.02
I_{2D}/I_G	0.81 ± 0.02	0.63 ± 0.03	0.56 ± 0.02

Table 2: Mean ratio of the D- to G-peak and 2D- to G-peak intensities and respective standard error of the different powder materials.

The specific surface area of the two graphene materials was determined using BET theory and is given in Table 3. The data shows that frGO has a slightly smaller specific surface area than rGO. Possible reasons for this could be that the plasma processing may reduce the size of the frGO particles to some extent, or that it may roughen the surface of the frGO particles in such a way that the depressions are too small to adsorb the nitrogen atoms. Another possible explanation could be that the reactive groups which are present at the surface of the graphene particles could hinder the adsorption of the nitrogen atoms.

	rGO	frGO
BET specific surface area (m^2/g)	317.5	306.4

Table 3: BET specific surface area of the graphene powder samples.

3.2 Evaluation of dispersion process

The used three roll mill enables an evaluation of the occurring line pressures within the two gaps to approximate the ease of dispersion. Figure 4 demonstrates the respective peak line pressure arising in the first gap during the consecutive cycles. It can be concluded that higher graphene loadings and rGO instead of frGO lead to higher forces during the dispersion process. Decreasing gap widths lead to increasing peak line pressures. If using a constant gap width between two consecutive cycles, the respective peak line pressure tends to decrease as the processing of the suspension within the three roll mill leads to a breakup of the particle aggregates.

Figure 4: Respective peak line pressure occurring in the first gap of a three roll mill during the respective cycle to disperse different loadings of graphene materials in the used epoxy resin.

3.3 Differential scanning calorimetry

The reaction enthalpy of pristine polymer and nanocomposite samples was evaluated using DSC and is illustrated in Figure 5. In comparison to the pristine polymer, the reaction enthalpy was increased significantly by approximately 13 % when including 0.5 wt% of frGO and by approximately 9 % when adding 0.5 wt% of rGO into the polymeric matrix. No significant change of the reaction enthalpy was observed between the frGO-including and rGO-including nanocomposites.

Figure 5: Mean reaction enthalpy and respective standard error of the pristine polymer and nanocomposite samples with different graphene loadings at a heating rate of 10 °C/min.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a characterization of rGO and frGO particles which underwent a plasma treatment was carried out. This plasma treatment had an effect on the morphology and the chemical composition of the surface of the particles resulting in a rougher surface as well as lower carbon and higher oxygen contents when comparing the plane of rGO with the frGO particle. The frGO particles and the edges of rGO demonstrate similar characteristics. The level of defects and specific surface area was only marginally affected by the plasma treatment. Furthermore, an evaluation of the dispersion process showed that the frGO particles tend to disperse more easily than the rGO particles without the necessity of adding other chemicals such as solvents which would require additional processing steps. As expected, higher loadings of rGO or frGO as well as decreasing gap widths increase the occurring line pressures during the dispersion process. When comparing the pristine polymer with the nanocomposite materials, the reaction enthalpy during curing was increased by 13 % in the case of 0.5 wt% frGO and by 9 % in the case of 0.5 wt% rGO. For the definition of suitable processing conditions, further characterization will need to evaluate the effect of rGO and frGO on e.g. the viscosity of the uncured nanocomposite, the reaction enthalpy, and the peak temperature during curing.

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